

A Curriculum Learning Approach for Improving Constraint Handling in Reinforcement Learning Applications to Spacecraft Guidance and Control

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This paper presents a general reward function formulation for efficiently addressing a fuel-optimal spacecraft guidance and control problem via reinforcement learning, which integrates the ε -constraint method as a form of curriculum learning to incrementally enforce constraints during training. Results from a benchmark problem demonstrate that this curriculum learning approach significantly enhances both constraint satisfaction and control optimality, providing a promising solution to the limitations of traditional RL techniques in space guidance applications.

1 Introduction

In recent years, deep learning techniques have become increasingly popular within the aerospace community to address a variety of complex engineering problems. One of the most thriving research topics is the application of DL to spacecraft guidance and control [1]. In this case, a closed-loop control law is built through a deep neural network (DNN), which generally maps an estimate of the spacecraft state provided by a navigation filter to the thrust control. When using RL as the training method, the optimization problem is posed as a Markov decision process (MDP). The optimization is driven by the reward function, which provides a measure of the effectiveness of the control policy in term of the current spacecraft state. During training, data about the environment, in the form of state-control-reward tuples, are collected via repeated simulations of the considered mission scenario, allowing for a progressive improvement of the control policy.

One of the main limitations of RL techniques lies in the fact that the MDP formulation allows for scalar reward functions only. Merit index, path constraints, and terminal constraints of the original optimal control problem (OCP) must be combined in a single scalar function, making it hard to meet the constraints

with a good accuracy level and, at the same time, achieve nearly optimal solutions. This paper aims to address this limitation by introducing a general formulation of a fuel-optimal spacecraft guidance and control problem as an MDP, which allows for the use of a constraint relaxation method, the ε -constraint method [2, 3], as a curriculum learning approach to gradually enforce constraints during training. Numerical results obtained on a benchmark problem, namely a soft pin-point planetary landing, show the performance improvement obtained when using the proposed curriculum learning technique in terms of constraint satisfaction and control optimality over standard formulation MDP formulation of the OCP.

2 Problem Statement

2.1 Optimal Control Problem

The spacecraft is modeled as a dynamic system with its state at time t represented by the vector $\mathbf{x}(t) = [\mathbf{r}^\top, \mathbf{v}^\top, m]^\top$, which includes its position, velocity, and mass. The state evolution from the initial time t_0 to the final time t_f follows first-order differential equations dependent on the state $\mathbf{x}(t)$, the control vector $\mathbf{u}(t)$ (thrust), and time t

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), t) \quad (1)$$

Generally, the system trajectory is constrained by path constraints

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), t) \leq 0 \quad (2)$$

A common example is the constraint on maximum allowable thrust

$$\|\mathbf{u}(t)\| \leq \mathbf{u}_{\max}, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, t_f] \quad (3)$$

Initial conditions are usually fully specified

$$\mathbf{x}(t_0) = \mathbf{x}_0 \quad (4)$$

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whereas the terminal state can be arbitrarily constrained

$$\chi(\mathbf{x}(t_f), \mathbf{u}(t_f), t_f) = 0 \quad (5)$$

The problem goal is determining the control law \mathbf{u}^* that minimizes the fuel consumption or equivalently maximizes the final spacecraft mass, hence $J = m(t_f)$.

Eventually, the fuel-optimal spacecraft guidance and control problem can be formulated as

$$P: \begin{cases} \max_{\mathbf{u}} m(t_f) \\ \text{s.t. (1)–(3), } t_0 \leq t \leq t_f \\ \quad (4), (5) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

2.2 Markov Decision Process

An MDP models a discrete-time optimal control process, described by the tuple $\langle X, A, \Phi, \mathbf{x}_0, R, d, K_{\max}, \gamma \rangle$, where X and A represent the state and action spaces, respectively. The transition dynamics $\mathbf{x}' = \Phi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{a}, t, t')$ defines the likelihood of moving to state \mathbf{x}' at time t' after applying action \mathbf{a} in state \mathbf{x} . The reward function $R(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{x}')$ assigns a scalar reward for the transition from \mathbf{x} to \mathbf{x}' , reflecting the suitability of the last action \mathbf{a} . The termination function $d(\mathbf{x})$ indicates if \mathbf{x} is the last state in the trajectory. K_{\max} is the maximum trajectory length, and γ is the discount factor.

The MDP aims to find a policy $\pi(\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{y})$ that maximizes the expected cumulative discounted reward, or return, over a trajectory τ

$$J = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{k=1}^K \gamma^{k-1} R_k \right] \quad (7)$$

where K is the step k meeting the following condition

$$d(\mathbf{x}_K) \vee K = K_{\max} \quad (8)$$

When translating an OCP as in Eq. (6) into an MDP, the total time t_f is divided into K_{\max} control steps, each of duration $\Delta t = t_f/K_{\max}$. The state transition dynamics are obtained by integrating the equations of motion

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \Phi(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, t_k, t_{k+1}) = \mathbf{x}_k + \int_{t_k}^{t_{k+1}} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}_k, t) dt \quad (9)$$

The objective function, path constraints, and terminal constraints of the original OCP must be integrated into the scalar reward function $R_k = R(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}, \mathbf{a}_{k-1}, \mathbf{x}_k)$. This function, in general, can be decomposed into a frequent $R_{f,k}$, delayed R_d , and penalty R_p term

$$R_k = \begin{cases} R_{f,k} & \text{if } k < K_{\max} \text{ and } d(\mathbf{x}_k) = 0 \\ R_{f,k} + R_d & \text{if } k = K_{\max} \text{ and } d(\mathbf{x}_k) = 0 \\ R_{f,k} + R_d + R_p & \text{if } d(\mathbf{x}_k) = 1 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

A possible choice to handle path constraints is to put a limit ψ_{\max} on the value that they can reach along a trajectory and trigger the termination function d when one of these values is exceeded

$$d(\mathbf{x}_k) = (\max\{\psi_k - \psi_{\max}\} > 0) \quad (11)$$

The reward function components can be designed to manage the mass consumption and the constraints satisfaction in the following way

$$R_{f,k} = w_m(m_{k+1} - m_k) - \max\{w_c^\top(\psi_k - \varepsilon_c)\}^+ \quad (12)$$

$$R_d = -\max\{w_b^\top(|\chi| - \varepsilon_b)\}^+ \quad (13)$$

$$R_p = -w_p w_c^{(j)} \psi_{\max}^{(j)} (K_{\max} - k) \quad (14)$$

where ε_c and ε_b represent the allowable deviations for meeting the path and terminal constraints, ψ and χ , respectively. The index j identifies the position of the greatest element of vector $\psi_k - \psi_{\max}$. The weights w_c , w_b , and w_p are used to adjust the importance of the various elements in the reward function. This general structure of the reward function has been validated in several studies on spacecraft guidance and control via RL [4–6], demonstrating its effectiveness in achieving similar results to those obtained via traditional optimal control methods.

The control policy π can also be designed to ensure that the action \mathbf{a}_k meets the maximum control magnitude in Eq. (3)

$$\mathbf{a}_k = [a_{k,\text{norm}} \mathbf{a}_{k,\text{dir}}^\top]^\top \sim \pi(\cdot|\mathbf{x}_k) \quad (15)$$

The corresponding control will be

$$\mathbf{u}_k = a_{k,\text{norm}} \frac{\mathbf{a}_{k,\text{dir}}}{\|\mathbf{a}_{k,\text{dir}}\|} \quad (16)$$

So, the general formulation of a fuel-optimal spacecraft guidance and control problem as an MDP is the following

$$M: \begin{cases} \max_{\pi} (7) \\ \text{s.t. (9), (15), (16), } k = 0, \dots, K-1 \\ \quad (10) - (14), \quad k = 1, \dots, K \\ \quad (4), (8) \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

3 Methodology

3.1 Reinforcement Learning

A policy gradient Deep Reinforcement learning (DRL) method has been used to solve the problem. Starting from a randomly chosen control policy π_θ , modeled as a fully connected deep neural network (DNN) of

weights and biases θ , we aim at finding the control policy that maximizes the total return in expectation.

The training procedure alternates between collecting data through environment interactions (policy rollout) and optimizing the policy (policy update) over a set number of iterations I . Each rollout gathers a fixed number n^{train} of observation-action-reward tuples using the latest policy π_θ . The collected data are then split into batches of n^{batch} steps each for training. Network parameters are updated via n^{opt} stochastic gradient ascent steps using a learning rate α , targeting the objective function J whose gradient is estimated with an empirical average over the batch. This study utilizes the proximal policy optimization (PPO) algorithm [7], a policy gradient method highly effective for continuous control tasks, including spacecraft guidance and control, as supported by extensive literature [4, 6, 8]. PPO enhances learning stability using a clipped-policy objective function that limits policy updates to occur within a fixed range, ϵ , called the clip range, preventing large performance oscillations.

3.2 Curriculum Learning

One key challenge of using RL to address an OCP is its inherent inability to separately address terminal and path constraints, unlike traditional optimal control methods. Instead, all constraints must be incorporated as weighted penalty terms in the reward function, necessitating careful and typically time-consuming tuning of these weights to prevent the emergence of suboptimal solutions.

Reward shaping [9] is frequently employed in RL applications to optimal control, including aerospace guidance problems [10, 11], to address the aforementioned challenges and speed up the learning process. This technique makes use of prior knowledge of the problem solution to tune the reward function, ensuring the trajectories remain aligned with this reference during training, typically designed to satisfy all problem constraints. While reward shaping is efficient in terms of sample usage, it depends on having some understanding of the optimal solution or exact solutions from relaxed versions of the problem [12, 13].

An alternative method, inspired by natural learning processes, involves gradually increasing the complexity of the problem during training by adapting the reward function. This approach, known as curriculum learning [14], allows the policy to progressively master a problem that might be too challenging to tackle in its initial formulation. In the realm of constrained OCPs, a curriculum learning can be exploited to enable a phased approach to learn how to meet the problem constraints while optimizing its objective.

This work proposes the use of the ϵ -constraint

technique [2], originally formulated for global optimization via metaheuristic algorithms [3], as such curriculum learning strategy. When applying the ϵ -constraint technique to RL, path and terminal constraints in the reward function are progressively enforced during training by gradually lowering their satisfaction tolerance, defined as ϵ , till the desired value. This approach gradually reduces the feasible region of the solution space. In the earliest stage of the optimization process, the algorithm is allowed to explore most of the search space, driven by the objective function component of the reward only. As the training progresses, tighter constraints are enforced, and the learning algorithm slowly adjusts its control policy to maintain feasibility. This incremental learning strategy increases the likelihood that the optimization discovers feasible solutions closer to the global optimum.

In this study, the ϵ -constraint technique is applied by setting the tolerances ϵ_c and ϵ_b for path and terminal constraints as in Eqs. (10)-(14) as functions of a single nondimensional hyperparameter ϵ , which is exponentially reduced during training from an initial value ϵ_0 to a target value ϵ_f

$$\epsilon_c = \epsilon \lambda_c, \quad \epsilon_b = \epsilon \lambda_b, \quad \epsilon = \epsilon_0 \left(\epsilon_f / \epsilon_0 \right)^{i/I} \quad (18)$$

where λ_c and λ_b are scaling factors, i is the current iteration, and I is the total number of iterations. For fuel-optimal problems, the current ϵ value can also be used to adjust the weight w_m of the propellant consumption term in the reward function Eq. (12) to ensure a balanced impact between the objective function and constraint violation terms as ϵ diminishes. The weight w_m is defined as $w_m = \lambda_m \epsilon$.

4 Results

The case study of the paper is a 3D adaptation of a landing problem in Ref. [15]. All data are nondimensional. A spacecraft of initial mass $m_0 = 1$, equipped with a chemical engine capable of maximum thrust $u_{\text{max}} = 1.227$ and effective exhaust velocity $v_{\text{eq}} = 2.349$, has to achieve a precise, soft landing on a planet without an atmosphere, minimizing fuel use over a fixed mission duration $t_f = 1.397$. The spacecraft state x at any time t includes its mass m , position $r = [x y z]^T$, and velocity $v = [v_x v_y v_z]^T$ relative to a target-centered frame. The initial spacecraft state is scattered around the position $r_0 = [0 0 1]^T$ and velocity $v_0 = [0 0 -0.783]^T$ with an amplitude of 0.4 along x, y , and z , and of 0.312 in v_x, v_y , and v_z . During descent, the spacecraft faces a constant gravitational acceleration $g = -g\hat{z}$ with $g = 1$. The final position and velocity must both reach a null value. The values of the

Table 1: Results of the Monte Carlo simulations.

Policy	$\Delta r_f, [10^{-3}]$				$\Delta v_f, [10^{-3}]$				m_p			
	mean	1- σ	2- σ	3- σ	mean	1- σ	2- σ	3- σ	mean	1- σ	2- σ	3- σ
w/o ϵ	2.275	3.459	4.643	5.827	0.425	0.725	1.024	1.324	0.668	0.688	0.708	0.728
w/ ϵ	1.560	1.979	2.397	2.815	0.486	0.867	1.248	1.629	0.643	0.666	0.689	0.712
GPOPS-II	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.629	0.638	0.661	0.673

Figure 1: Trajectories obtained with the two policies.

Figure 2: Control laws obtained with the two policies.

hyperparameters in the reward function are $\lambda_m = 1$, $\lambda_b = \mathbf{w}_b = [1 \ 1]^\top$, $\epsilon_0 = 1$, $\epsilon_f = 10^{-3}$, $I = 20000$.

A fully-connected neural network, with three layers and 256 neurons per layer, has been used as control policy. PPO is run with a clip range of $\epsilon = 0.0025$ and a learning rate of $\alpha = 10^{-4}$. The policy network has been trained twice from scratch on the problem under consideration, one time with the ϵ -constraint active, and the second time without ϵ -constraint, i.e., by fixing $\epsilon_0 = \epsilon_f = 10^{-3}$, in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed curriculum learning approach. The closed-loop performance of the two trained policies are evaluated by means of a 1000-trajectory Monte Carlo analysis. The main statistics of these analyses are summarized in Table 1. Specifically, for each con-

trol policy, Table 1 reports the mean value and the 1- σ , 2- σ , and 3- σ values of the final distance Δr_f from the landing point, final velocity error Δv_f , and total propellant mass m_p . For comparison, the propellant mass obtained with a direct optimal control method using the software GPOPS-II [16] is also included. Figure 1 and 2 show the Monte Carlo trajectories, and the corresponding thrust laws, obtained with the two policies.

5 Discussion

The obtained results confirm that RL with the ϵ -constraint technique outperforms standard RL in terms of final position accuracy in all four metrics. Notably, the mean error in position is reduced by 31%, and the landing point dispersion by 52% (3- σ value). When looking at the final lander velocity, the two policies attain very close mean values, 50% lower than the considered accuracy threshold (10^{-3}). The dispersion in terminal velocity is slightly wider when curriculum learning is used (about 19% in 3 σ value) but still much closer to the desired accuracy than the position counterpart obtained with no ϵ -constraint. However, the biggest advantage of using the ϵ -constraint approach is in terms of trajectory optimality. One can notice that the trajectories obtained with curriculum learning consistently feature a lower propellant mass consumption (by about 4%) both in mean value and in the three σ values, closer to the globally optimal values obtained via a traditional optimal control method. Indeed, by looking at the thrust law profiles in Fig. 2, when the ϵ -constraint is active, the control tends to follow a pattern more similar to a bang-off-bang solution, with the thrust almost always at its maximum value but for the initial and terminal part of the landing, as it is expected in a fuel optimal problem with dynamics affine in the control variables [15]. The optimal thrust law for a completely vertical descent obtained via GPOPS-II is reported in red as a reference. This closeness to optimality of the ϵ -constraint approach is also confirmed by the shape of the obtained trajectories (Fig. 1), which feature a more symmetrical distribution around the vertical axis, which is the expected optimal behavior, given the problem symmetry.

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